

1 **Metalloproteinases of the ADAMTS family are components of the TE differentiation program in an**
2 **iPS model of lineage specification in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
9 metalloproteinases of the ADAMTS family as lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic stem
10 cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

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